

THE PREVALENCE OF NEONATAL TETANUS IN UNIVERSITY OF CALABAR TEACHING HOSPITAL
(UCTH) MATERNITY ANNEX

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ABSTRACT

Neonatal tetanus is a preventable disease which is still a public health problem in developing countries. The purpose of this study was to determine the prevalence of neonatal tetanus in maternity Annex from 2003 – 2007. One hypothesis and two research questions were formulated to guide the study. The target population for the study was all sick babies on admission within this period. Data was collected through records. Data was analyzed using simple percentages and chi – square statistics. The findings revealed a high prevalence of tetanus cases 39 (15.7%) in 2005 while the highest number of death 22 (61.1%) occurred in 2003. chi square analysis showed a significant relationship between immunization status of mothers and neonatal tetanus development (χ^2 call 28.05 $>$ χ^2 tab 7.81, df 3 $P \geq 0.05$). It is recommended that intensive antenatal education be given to women in order to reduce the ignorance associated with the causes of the disease.

KEYWORDS: Prevalence, neonatal tetanus.

INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY:

Tetanus is an acute, often fatal disease that is characterized by generalized increased rigidity and convulsive spasms of skeletal muscles (Vandelaer et al, 2008). It is caused by the spore-forming bacterium *Clostridium tetani*. *Clostridium tetani* spores (the dormant form of the organism) are found in soil (. Neonatal tetanus is one of the six childhood killer diseases and a major contributory factor in neonatal death especially in developing countries. Neonatal tetanus is a preventable disease that is still a public health problem especially in rural areas of the developing countries UNICEF (2003). This disease occurs within a few days or weeks of birth as a result of the infection of the umbilical stump by ‘bacterium-clostridium tetanus’ due to poor hygienic and traditional birth practices.

According to World Health Organization (WHO, 2000), this infection occurs due to unskilled attendance at delivery, which is reported to be about 69%. It is also reported that high illiteracy rate, cutting and treatment of the umbilical and with potentially infected materials like “tradition knife” or used blade, cow dung, saliva and lack of immunization of pregnant women against tetanus contribute to the development of neonatal tetanus. WHO (2001) and Garb et al (2008) report that this disease occurs because most deliveries take place at home or in spiritual churches with the assistance of untrained traditional birth attendants.

Reduction of child mortality is one of the Seven Points Agenda for Nigeria. This agenda says that for 2015 target to be met, the country would need to reduce the rate of infant/child mortality to less than 28 per 1,000. According to National Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) (2003) infant mortality rate is estimated at 109 per 1,000. Urban areas according to this survey had infant mortality rates of 81 per 1,000 compared to 121 per 1,000 for rural areas. This confirms that infant mortality rate is higher by communities where health and social services are poor.

In a study conducted by Okoromah *et al* (2003) at Lagos University Teaching Hospital (LUTH), neonatal tetanus was among the highest causes of infant mortality in the hospital. WHO, UNICEF and UNPFA (2000) observed that to achieve the global goal of neonatal tetanus, reduction, renewed commitment from African region and external financial support to immunize 60 million women of child bearing age and proper counseling during antenatal care in high – risk areas is essential. WHO (1999) reports that an estimated 248,000 deaths from neonatal tetanus occurred in 1997 primarily among babies in Africa and South East Asia whose mothers had limited access to routine health services offering tetanus immunization and hygienic delivery condition. According to the National Demographic and Health Survey (2003) and National Population Commission and ORC Macro, Calverton MD, (2004) the

neonatal mortality rate (deaths of infants within the first 28 days of life) is reported to be 48 per 1000 live births, with wide regional variations in the distribution of neonatal mortality in a pattern that mirrors that seen with maternal mortality. Neonatal death rate is related to problems arising during pregnancy, delivery and after delivery. Neonatal mortality related to maternal and obstetric factors

Studies report that the majority of the new born deaths in Nigeria occur within the first week of life reflecting the intimate link of new born survival to the quality of maternal care. Neonatal deaths are also strongly linked in terms of place of birth and access to care. Infant mortality rate is widely used as one of the most single measures of health status of a community. Neonatal tetanus was reported to contribute 10.3% in the estimated causes of death in infants therefore ranking 1st in the causes of death (NDHS 2003) among other causes of death in infants like severe infections including pneumonia, sepsis and diarrhoeal disease. Key determinants of newborn mortality in Nigeria include inadequate coverage and the low quality of essential obstetric care. It is expected that with the establishment of maternal and child health services infant morbidity and mortality should fall from being very high (Lucas and Gills (1990). Since good health can respond dramatically to simple preventive measures. In a study conducted by Federal Ministry Health & United National Population Fund (UNFPA) (2003) on the quality of care, only 18.5% of 4500 facilities surveyed had the capacity to provide obstetric care. Even where the skilled attendants were available, poor inter – personal – relations have been reported to impact negatively on the utilization of services by women. This factor gives rise to most women delivering at home or in churches.

Financial access like poverty has significant implications for health and development; low income households generally have poorer health status. It also shows striking differences in different socioeconomic groups. The incidence of poverty is higher in the rural areas where neonatal tetanus rate is reported also to be higher than in the urban areas. Increasing health care costs have resulted in substantial decrease in the utilization of maternal health services.

Socio – cultural factors (beliefs and practices) limit the ability of women to utilize ante natal education given to them as well as take independent decision about their babies. The decision making power often lies with mothers or mothers – in-laws or other senior female relatives especially among primiparas makes women helpless in matters concerning their children's health.

Education another key factor has been shown to be highly associated with health seeking behaviour in pregnancy and delivery. Neonatal tetanus rates are much higher in infants whose mothers have no education compared to women with secondary level or higher education. Access to mass media is also important for acquiring information and knowledge on maternal and neonatal health issues. In a study conducted by NDHS (2003) the proportion of women that had access to any mass media was about two to three times that of men in the rural and urban areas. The fact that more than half of the women do not have access to any mass media is likely to affect pregnancy and delivery and consequently neonatal mortality occurrence (UNICEF, 2001). Other channels of communication including interpersonal communication are important in passing on key health messages to the community. If these channels are properly utilized women will turn – up for antenatal care and delivered at the health facilities available (Federal Ministry Of Health (FMOH), 2007).

Materials and Methods.

This was a retrospective study using records and questionnaire. The records covering a period from January 2003 – December 2007 in the Sick Babies' Unit (Maternity Annex) of the University of Calabar Teaching Hospital, Calabar were used.

DATA COLLECTION

Data collection was through records of new born admissions and structured questionnaire given to the mothers of babies on admission between January and March, 2008.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using simple percentages and chi-square statistics.

RESULTS

The data in Table 1 shows the record of annual admissions of neonates, admissions with neonatal tetanus and annual neonatal death due to tetanus between January, 2003 and December, 2007. A total number of 1629 neonates were admitted into the maternity Annex. Out of this number, 166 of them were admitted with neonatal tetanus with 87 neonatal deaths. The highest NNT admission occurred in 2005 with 39 deaths representing 18 (9.2%) of the total neonatal mortality caused by tetanus. This was followed by the year 2003 which recorded 36 neonatal tetanus admission with 22 (8.5%) mortality. Table revealed the annual prevalence of neonatal tetanus in the Maternity Annex during the period under study. The result shows that majority of the NNT admission and deaths occurred believes the months of March and June 20 (17%) and 22 (11.2%) respectively.

Table shows mortality of neonates from tetanus within the period under study. The mortality occurred mostly in 2003 with 22 (8.5%) of the total death in that year. This was followed by 19 (5%).

Table 4 shows the relationship between mothers' immunization status and the risk of neonatal tetanus development. The result shows a significant relationship as $\chi^2_{cal} 28.06 > \chi^2_{tab} 3.84$ df 1 at probability level of 0.05.

In table 5, the relationship between age of mothers and NNT development. The table shows a significant relationship as $\chi^2_{cal} 7.94 > \chi^2_{tab} 5.99$, df 2 at probability level of 0.06.

Table 6 shows the socio – demographic data of 51 randomly selected files containing mothers' information. The age distribution shows that majority of the mothers were between the age range 20-29 years 21 (41.2%). This was followed by mothers with age range 30-39 (years 19 (37.3%). The table also shows majority of the mothers to be Christians 38 (74.5%) with 10 (19.6%) being Muslim, 25 (49%) mothers were single 21 (41.2%) married while 29 (56.9%) had their 1st child and 15 (29.4%) had 2 – 3 children. Educational status revealed that 12 (23.53%) mothers had no formal education while 10 (19.61%) had primary education, JSS and SSS each represented 12 (23.53%) occupational status shows that majority of the mothers were students 18 (35.3%).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The findings of this study indicated that there is fluctuation but with a gradual decline in the number of NNT admissions which also mirrors the number of death in the study. This could be due to some improvement in the quality of care rendered and the availability of Tetanus toxoid immunization activities available in health centers. The results in table 4 shows significant relationship between mothers. Immunization. Status and risk of developing neonatal tetanus. This finding is supported by Udoh (1994) and Antia Obong *et al* (1992) who report that neonatal tetanus occurs because most deliveries take place at home or in spiritual riches. The findings also show that infant mortality due to neonatal tetanus is high compare to other causes of neonatal mortality. This is in line with the findings of a study by Okoromah *et al* (2003) in LUTH. Who reported that neonatal tetanus was one of the highest causes of infant mortality. This is typical of infant mortality in rural communities where poverty, illiteracy, cultural practices and lack of access to the health care facilities are partly responsible for the causes of NNT. The high Neonatal deaths due neonatal tetanus may be due to inability to attend antenatal to by unskilled health personnel at home before being taken to the hospital in critical conditions (Garb *et al*, 2008 and NDHS, 2005). As could be seen in this study table 4, majority of the mothers 126 were not immunized against tetanus during pregnancy thus exposing their babies to the risk developing the disease.

Table 2 shows yearly prevalence of the disease. From the findings, it can be observed that neonatal tetanus is expected to be seen occasionally if it must be seen at all, but it is sad to note the high percentage (55.5%) of neonatal morbidity that is due to the disease alone. This is also reported in NDHS (2005) survey where it was observed that only 18.5% of 4500 facilities surveyed in the country had the capacity to provide obsteric care that can reduce the occurrence of some of these problems.

Table1: Showing monthly and yearly distribution of neonatal admissions and deaths (2003 – 2007)

	2003 TOTAL NNT DEATH ADM	2004 TOTAL NNT DEATH ADM	2005 TOTAL NNT DEATH ADM	2006 TOTAL NNT DEATH ADM	2007 TOTAL NNT DEATH ADM	TOTAL TOTAL NNT DEATH ADM
Jan.	- - -	22 2 1	- - -	27 4 3	25 1 1	74 7 5
Feb.	- - -	40 3 1	12 2 1	26 4 2	46 2 1	125 11 5
Mar.	32 10 7	34 6 4	28 6 4	34 5 1	38 1 1	166 28 17
April	22 1 -	33 4 3	25 3 2	30 2 -	25 - -	135 10 5
May	26 7 4	37 2 2	30 7 1	41 1 1	27 1 -	161 18 8
June	24 2 1	27 6 2	28 5 3	34 5 3	33 4 2	146 22 11
July	20 2 1	15 2 1	17 5 2	25 4 2	35 1 1	112 14 7
Aug.	25 2 2	25 3 1	26 6 3	49 4 -	59 4 1	184 19 7
Sept.	21 4 3	21 3 1	18 - -	36 3 4	44 2 -	140 12 8
Oct.	29 2 1	18 1 1	16 1 -	31 3 2	44 3 3	138 10 7
Nov.	31 2 -	- - -	24 1 -	28 1 1	38 2 1	121 6 2
Dec.	30 4 3	Strike	24 3 2	36 1 -	37 1 -	127 9 5
TOTAL	260 36 22	272 32 17	249 39 18	397 37 19	451 22 11	1629 166 87

Table 2: Showing yearly prevalence of Neonatal tetanus (2003 -2007)

Year	Total no of infant admission	Total no of NNT	Prevalence percentage
2003	260	36	13.9
2004	272	32	11.8
2005	249	39	15.7
2006	397	37	9.3
2007	451	22	4.9
Total	1629	116	55.5

Table3: Showing mortality from Neonatal tetanus (2003-2007)

Year	No of NNT admitted	No of death	Total No of admission	Percentage
2003	36	22	260	8.5
2004	32	17	272	6.3
2005	39	18	249	9.2
2006	37	19	397	5
2007	22	11	451	5
Total	166	87	1629	34%

Table 4: Showing immunization status of mothers and risk of neonatal tetanus development

Immunization status	Development of tetanus				Total	Cal x ²	df	Crit x ²
	Yes		No					
	O	E	O	E				
Immunized	40	105.9	1000	934.0	1040	28.08*	1	3.84
Not immunized	126	60	463	528.9	589			
Total	166		1463		1619			

$X^2 \text{ cal} = 28.6$ $X^2 \text{ tab} = 3.84$ $P > 0.05$

*Significant at 0.5 probability level

Table 5: Showing relationship between age of mothers and NNT development

Age of mothers	Neonatal Development				Total	x ² Cal	df	Critical x ²
	Yes		No					
	O	E	O	E				
20 – 29	97	101.5	900	895.4	997	7.94	2	5.99
30 – 39	51	37.8	320	333.1	371			
40 and above	18	26.5	243	234.4	261			
Total	166		1463		1629			

*Significant at .05 probability level.

$X^2 \text{ cal} = 7.94$, $X^2 \text{ tab} = 5.99$, $P > 0.05$

Mothers' age was observed to have a significant relationship with the risk of developing neonatal tetanus. From the study most mothers (97) between age range 20 – 29, had babies with the diseases. There was a gradual decrease in the disease occurrence as the mothers age increased. This could be related to the fact that most women under marital status were single and may not have had any support or someone to advice them on the useness of antenatal care.

This finding could also be related to the fact that most deaths due to NNT occurred among mothers who were primi para (have 1st child).

Implication for nursing practice.

The findings of the study show that neonatal tetanus is still a serious public health problem due to the high number of reported cases in UCTH Calabar which is a tertiary health care institution. If this number is observed in this hospital, then number not reported by mothers in the communities will be alarming. Nurses are who are found in all the highways and by way rendering care must ensure that mothers are given care in their door post as one of the primary health objectives emphasis.

The nurse thus can play several roles to ensure a reduction in neonatal mortality especially neonatal tetanus.

The nurse should make conscious efforts to educate mothers especially in the communities about the changers of not attending antenatal care some socio – cultural practices that results in NNT.

The nurses should ensure that proper information is given to mothers during antenatal education.

Table 6: Socio – demographic data of mothers from the files.

Variable	No of Respondents	Percentage
<u>Age</u>		41.2
20 - 29	21	37.3
30 – 39	19	21.5
40 and above	11	
Total	51	100
<u>Religion</u>		
Christianity	38	74.5
Muslim	10	19.6
Traditional religion	3	5.9
Total	51	100
<u>Marital Status</u>		
Single	25	49.0
Married	21	41.2
Divorce	4	7.8
Widow	1	2.0
Total	51	100
<u>Number of children</u>		
1 st child	29	56.9
2 – 3	15	29.4
4 and above	7	13.7
Total	51	100
<u>Educational Status</u>		
No formal education	12	23.53
Primary	10	19.61
Junior secondary	12	23.53
Senior secondary	5	9.80
Tertiary		
Total	51	100
<u>Occupation</u>		
Student	18	35.3
Civil Servant	8	15.7
Farmer	7	13.7
Housewife	9	17.6
Trader	9	17.6
Total	51	100

He/she can supply information for health statistics by keeping proper records.

The nurse as a patient advocate must ensure proper precautionary measures in the care of clients be it in the hospital or in the community.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study revealed that neonatal tetanus is still a public health problem inspite of the fact that so much is preached about National Immunization in the country.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the above findings, the following are recommended:

Intensive health education programme and public health enlightenment should be embarked upon on the dangers of not attending antenatal care to reduce the rate of neonatal death especially due to tetanus.

Adequate qualified midwives as well as other health personnel should be provided in the communities to provide regular prenatal, antenatal and postnatal care to women.

Woman should be encouraged to attend antenatal clinic where health education about their health and their unborn babies is given.

Women should be encouraged to deliver their babies in the clinic/hospital and also attend postnatal clinics regularly.

The traditional birth attendance should be trained especially on the dangers of not using precautionary measures in the management of mothers in labour and delivery.

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